

Equilibrium Study of the Mixed Complex of Copper(II) with 2-Hydroxynicotinic and Salicylic Acids

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The complexation equilibria between copper(II), 2-hydroxynicotinic acid (hyna) and salicylic acid (sa) have been studied using spectrophotometric and potentiometric pH-titration methods in ethanol-water medium (50%, v/v; $I=0.1 M$ NaClO₄, 25°). Optimum conditions for the predominance of the complex forming equilibrium: $\text{Cu(hyna)} + \text{sa} \rightleftharpoons \text{Cu(hyna)(sa)}$ were established. The stability constant of the Cu(hyna)(sa) mixed-ligand complex was determined and the ternary complex enhancement over binary complex formation was evaluated. For the equilibrium: $\text{Cu(hyna)}_2 + \text{Cu(sa)}_2 \rightleftharpoons 2\text{Cu(hyna)(sa)}$, the corresponding constant was $\log X = +0.7 (+0.08)$. The constant given in parenthesis is due to $\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}} = \log K_{\text{Cu(hyna)(sa)}} - \log K_{\text{Cu(sa)}}$. The mixed complex absorbs strongly at 355 nm in the pH range 6.2–6.8 and the ternary system obey's Beer's law upto $6.5 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of copper with molar absorptivity of $0.84 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Although the complex forming ability of nicotinic acid has been the subject of several investigation¹⁻⁵, a few studies have been reported on the complexation equilibria of substituted nicotinic acids⁶⁻⁸. There is no study in the literature on the solution equilibria of metal chelates of hydroxynicotinic acids. Very recently we reported work in this aspect⁹. Based on preliminary results of the reactivity of this class of pyridinecarboxylic acids towards copper(II), 2-hydroxynicotinic acid (hyna) was chosen for detailed equilibrium study in ethanol-water medium.

In the present work, the complex formation between the 1:1 copper(II)-2-hydroxynicotinic acid complex and salicylic acid(sa) was investigated. The work was aimed to establish the complexation equilibria that exist in solution and characterising the stability of the biligand complex system using spectrophotometric and potentiometric methods. The enhancement of the Cu mixed-ligand complex over binary complex formation was evaluated. The use of the structurally related aromatic acid, sa, as a second ligand is due to its biological action. Moreover, it was desirable to know whether both the reagents behave analogously in mixed-ligand complexes.

Results and Discussion

Solution spectra and complexation equilibria: The spectroscopic, acid-base and chelating properties of hyna have been recently studied in this laboratory⁹⁻¹⁰. The predominant form of this reagent in 50% (v/v) ethanol at pH 3.5–5.0 is the nonionised form (LH₂). The transformation of the latter species to the mono-anionic form (LH⁻) is carried out in pH range 5.5–7.0. At higher pH, the formation of dianionic form of the reagent (L²⁻) is assumed. The acid dissociation constants of hyna were evaluated⁹, the $\text{p}K_{\text{LH}_2}^{\text{H}}$ value corres-

ponding to the release of the carboxyl proton was found to be 6.18 ± 0.01 whereas the value of $\text{p}K_{\text{LH}}^{\text{H}}$ for the hydroxyl proton was 9.58 ± 0.02 .

The solution spectra of the Cu^{II}-hyna 1:1 complex with the reagent blank as reference are characterised by absorption bands at 325 and 305 nm in the pH range 2.8–6.0. The spectral changes of solutions of the binary system as a function of pH have showed that the initial binary complex (CuLH⁺) is converted to the deprotonated complex species CuL at pH 4.5–5.6. The reaction of Cu^{II} with sa was cursorily investigated elsewhere¹¹⁻¹³. Neither sa nor its 1:1 Cu^{II} complex has measurable absorbance above 350 nm.

The spectrum of a solution containing equimolar concentrations of sa, hyna and Cu^{II} against a reagent blank with the same concentration of the two ligands, shows an absorption band at 355 nm in the pH range 6.2–6.8 (Fig. 1). This band is assumed to be due to the formation of a mixed-ligand complex of Cu^{II} with hyna and sa. The absorbances of solutions of the ternary system were measured as a function of pH at 305 and 355 nm; the maximum absorbance was attained at pH ~ 6.5.

The stoichiometry of the mixed-ligand complex was established by Job's method of continuous variation. The mole fractions of two of the components were varied continuously, keeping the third component in a large excess for all solutions in the series. Under these conditions, the ternary system was modified to quasi-binary system. The results obtained conclusively demonstrate that the overall Cu(hyna)(sa) complex has a 1:1:1 composition at the pH studied. The formation of the mixed complex was investigated at different pHs in presence of equimolar concentrations of components. The variation of absorbance with pH at 355 nm shows only one rising part in the pH

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of Cu^{II}-binary and ternary complexes (50% v/v, ethanol, pH=6.5): (a) hyna, (b) 1 : 1 Cu^{II}-hyna, (c) 1 : 1 Cu^{II}-sa and (d) 1 : 1 : 1 Cu-hyna-sa ; (b, c and d) against reagent blank.

range 6.2–6.8 (Fig. 2). The graph indicates a single equilibrium due to ternary complex formation asuming that the initial monoligand complex of Cu^{II}s with hyna was already formed at pH < 6. The complex equilibria depicted from the analysis of the absorbance vs pH graph of the ternary system at 305 and 355 nm can be represented by equations (1–3),

where LH₂ and RH⁻ represent the nonionised and monoanionic forms of hyna and sa respectively. The above scheme is based on the fact that the 1 : 1 2-hydroxynicotinic acid-copper(II) complex is the most stable complex in solution at pH < 6. Equation (3) may represent a transition of the Cu-hyna complex to a complex containing the competing ligand sa.

The direct graphical and logarithmic analysis¹⁴⁻¹⁶ of the absorbance vs pH plot at 355 nm confirms the existence of equilibrium (3). On the other hand, the analysis of the graph at 305 nm in the pH range 4.5–5.5 gives the best fit for equilibrium (2) containing the species CuL, whereas the results obtained for the second rising part of the graph are in tune with equation (3) and the formation of the CuLR complex species.

The number of liberated protons and the equilibrium constant corresponding to equation (3) were obtained from logarithmic transformation (4) reported elsewhere^{15,16}

$$\log [(A - \epsilon_1 C_M)Z / (\epsilon_2 C_M - A)] = q \text{ pH} + \log C_L + \log K^* \quad (4)$$

where $Z = 1 + k_{a2} / [H]$ and A is the absorbance of

Fig. 2. Absorbance vs pH graphs for Cu^{II}-sa (curve a) and Cu^{II}-hyna (curve b) binary systems and Cu^{II} hyna-sa (CuLR) ternary system (curves c and d), 50% (v/v) ethanol, (a) $C_M = C_R = 2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, $\lambda = 315 \text{ nm}$; (b) $C_M = C_L = 2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, $\lambda = 320 \text{ nm}$; (c) $C_M = C_L = C_R = 0.5 \times 10^{-4} M$, $\lambda = 355 \text{ nm}$ and (d) $C_M = C_L = C_R = 0.5 \times 10^{-4} M$, $\lambda = 305 \text{ nm}$.

test solution against reagent blank under the same conditions.

The stability constant of the CuLR mixed ligand complex is related to the equilibrium constant K^* by equation (5)

$$\log B = \log K^* + \log B_{\text{CuL}}^{\text{Cu}} + pK_{\text{RH}}^{\text{H}} \quad (3)$$

The calculated values of the equilibrium ($\log K^*$), stability constant ($\log B$) and molar absorptivity of the ternary copper complex with hyna and sa (CuLR) are given in Table 1. The ternary system

TABLE 1—MEAN VALUES OF EQUILIBRIUM, STABILITY CONSTANT AND MOLAR ABSORPTIVITY OF THE TERNARY COPPER COMPLEX WITH hyna AND sa (CuLR)

Ethanol : 50% (v/v), $I = 0.1 M$ (NaClO₄), Temp. = 25°

Equilibrium	Constant	log constant	Molar absorptivity $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$
$[\text{CuLR}][\text{H}]/[\text{CuL}][\text{RH}]$	K^*	3.35	0.84×10^4
$[\text{CuLR}]/[\text{Cu}][\text{L}][\text{R}]$	B	19.56	
$\log B = \log K^* + \log B_{\text{ML}}^{\text{M}} + pK_{\text{HR}}^{\text{H}}$			

obeyed Beer's law up to a concentration of $6.5 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of copper(II). A Ringbom plot¹⁷ showed that the optimal working range for Cu^{II} determination using the CuLR^{2-} mixed complex is between 1.25 and $5.1 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. The sensitivity of the reaction was calculated according to Sandell⁸ and was found to be $1.7 \times 10^{-8} \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ of copper. The reproducibility of the results was checked by analysing two series of eight solutions having Cu^{II} concentration of 2.0 and $4.5 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. The relative standard deviations obtained were found to be 0.72 and 0.55 respectively.

Potentiometric pH-titrations: All experimental conditions of the potentiometric pH-titrations were the same as described earlier¹⁸. The evaluation of the experimental data were done as given before¹⁹. The acid dissociation constants of hyna ($\text{p}K_{\text{LH}_2}^{\text{H}}$ (3-COOH), $\text{p}K_{\text{LH}}^{\text{H}}$ (2-OH)) and sa ($\text{p}K_{\text{RH}_2}^{\text{H}}$ due to the hydroxyl group) were determined in 50% (v/v) ethanol-water medium by titrating 50 ml of $2.5 \times 10^{-3} M \text{HClO}_4$ and NaClO_4 ($I=0.1M$) in the presence and absence of the ligand ($10^{-4}M$) with standard carbonate-free NaOH ($1 \times 10^{-2}M$). The stability constant of the binary complexes were calculated from titration graphs in which the metal to ligand ratio was 1:2. The conditions for the measurements were the same as for the acidity constants. Titrations of solutions without ligands were used as a basis for evaluation. The conditions of measurements for the titrations of the ternary system were the same as for the binary complexes, but the solutions contained equimolar amounts of hyna, Cu^{II} and sa. The titration curves were evaluated using the curves obtained with the same solutions but without sa. Multiple titrations were carried out for each system. The stability constants were calculated from six independent titration curves.

The potentiometric pH-titration graph for the ternary system containing Cu^{II} , hyna and sa in a 1:1:1 molar ratio exhibits a single step inflection at $m=3$ (where m =moles of alkali added per mole of metal ion).

Despite the apparently simple stoichiometry suggested for $\text{Cu}(\text{hyna})(\text{sa})$ mixed-ligand complex, its formation does not occur in one step as alkali is added. In addition to the formation of the deprotonated binary complex of Cu^{II} with hyna (CuL), the equilibria set in solution of the ternary system above pH 5 presumably involve the complex transitions (6) and (7),

The product K_6 , K_7 is equated to K_3 the equilibrium constant of reaction (3) which represents the formation of the 1:1:1 $\text{Cu}(\text{hyna})(\text{sa})$ ternary complex.

In the calculation of the stability constant due to the mixed-ligand complex ($K_{\text{CuLR}}^{\text{Cu}}$), it is assumed

that the complex formation between Cu^{II} and hyna is complete. The titration graph of the 1:1 Cu -hyna binary system indicates that when two equivalents of alkali are added, there is almost complete conversion of copper(II) and ligand to one-to-one Cu -hyna complex. Stoichiometry for complex formation consistent with alkali consumed is the removal of the carboxyl proton, in addition to that of the 2-OH group, producing the noncharged monoligand complex CuL .

Stability of the ternary complex: One way to quantify the stability of the ternary complex is by comparing the difference in stability according to equation (8)²⁰⁻²²,

$$\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}} = \log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{hyna})(\text{sa})}^{\text{Cu}} - \log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{sa})}^{\text{Cu}} \quad (8)$$

The overall stability constant $B_{\text{Cu}(\text{hyna})(\text{sa})}^{\text{Cu}}$ due to equilibrium (9) is connected with $K_{\text{Cu}(\text{hyna})(\text{sa})}^{\text{Cu}}$ by equation (10),

$$\log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{hyna})(\text{sa})}^{\text{Cu}} = \log B_{\text{Cu}(\text{hyna})(\text{sa})}^{\text{Cu}} - \log K_{\text{Cu}(\text{hyna})}^{\text{Cu}} \quad (10)$$

The value of $\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}}$ is the logarithm of the equilibrium constant of equation (7). Statistically, $\Delta \log K$ should have a value^{23,24} of -0.6 , values greater than this indicate a stabilisation of the ternary complex species. In the present work, it is obvious that ternary enhancement of the 1:1:1 species is favoured by the $\text{Cu}(\text{hyna})(\text{sa})$ system as shown by the positive value of $\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}}$.

The other approach used to quantify the stability of the ternary complex is based on the equilibrium constant, X , corresponding to equation (11)²¹, $\log X$ may be calculated according to equation (12),

$$X = B_{1s}^2 / B_2(\text{hyna}) \cdot B_2(\text{sa})$$

or,

$$\log X = 2 \log B_{\text{Cu}(\text{hyna})(\text{sa})}^{\text{Cu}} - [\log B_{\text{Cu}(\text{hyna})_2}^{\text{Cu}} + \log B_{\text{Cu}(\text{sa})_2}^{\text{Cu}}] \quad (12)$$

The statistical value for $\log X$ is the same for all geometries of the coordination sphere of a metal ion and is^{21,25} 0.6.

The experimental data of the potentiometric pH-titrations for the $\text{Cu}(\text{hyna})(\text{sa})$ ternary system may be described by equilibria (2) and (3).

The extent of ternary complex enhancement over binary complex formation for the 1:1:1 Cu -hyna-sa mixed complex can be recognised if one examines equilibrium reactions (3) and (7). The constants corresponding to equilibrium (3), K'_6 and (7), K'_7 are given by equations (13) and (14) respectively,

$$K'_6 = B_{\text{CuLR}}^{\text{Cu}} \cdot K_{\text{RH}}^{\text{H}} / B_{\text{CuL}}^{\text{Cu}} \quad (13)$$

$$K'_7 = B_{\text{CuLR}}^{\text{Cu}} / B_{\text{CuL}}^{\text{Cu}} \cdot B_{\text{CuR}}^{\text{Cu}} \quad (14)$$

The $\log K'_t$ and $\log K''_t$ have the values -3.35 and +0.08 respectively. This finding may suggest that the formation of 1 : 1 : 1 ternary copper(II) complex depends primarily on the formation of initial Cu-hyna complex and disproportionates at the pH at which the two binary species coexist. Since the CuR binary species is liable to set in solution of the ternary system at pH of approximately 5, the value of $\log K'_t$ reflects the stability of the mixed-ligand complex. It seems that the disproportionation of mono-ligand complexes to form the 1 : 1 : 1 ternary species is favoured as indicated by the positive value of $\log K'_t$. This is in line with our assumption that equation (3) represents the overall ternary complex forming reaction.

The acidity constants of the ligands and the stability constants of the binary Cu^{II} complexes which were used for the calculation of the stability constant of the ternary complex are given in Table 2. By using the results in Table 3 for the formation of the ternary complex, the values of $\Delta \log K_{Cu}$ and $\log X$ were calculated.

TABLE 2—ACIDITY CONSTANTS OF THE LIGANDS AND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THEIR BINARY Cu^{II} COMPLEXES

Ethanol : 50% (v/v), $I=0.1 M$ (NaClO₄), Temp. = 25°

Ligand (X)	pK _{a1}	pK _{a2}	$\log K_{CuX}^{Cu}$	$\log K_{CuX_2}^{Cu}$	$\log B_{CuX_2}^{Cu}$
hyna	6.18 ± 0.04	9.58 ± 0.02	9.05	10.37	19.42
sa	3.65 ± 0.01	13.86 ± 0.05	10.52	8.66	19.18

TABLE 3—EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS OF THE TERNARY Cu^{II}-hyna-sa COMPLEX AND SOME RELATED DATA

$\log B_{Cu(hyna)(sa)}^{Cu}$	$\log K_{Cu(hyna)(sa)}^{Cu}$	$\Delta \log K_{Cu}$	$\log X$
19.65	10.60	+0.08	+0.7

Experimental

Analytical grade reagents were used through out the present study and double distilled water was used for preparation of solutions. 2-Hydroxynicotinic acid (hyna) and salicylic acid (sa) (both Aldrich), HClO₄ and NaClO₄ (Merck) were used. A 5×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ stock solutions of hyna or sa were prepared in pure ethanol. A stock solution of copper(II) perchlorate was prepared using perchloric acid and copper carbonate and standardised by EDTA²⁷, while the carbonate-free NaOH solution was prepared and standardised by titrating with potassium hydrogen phthalate. The working solutions were prepared by accurate dilution. For spectral measurements, the acidity of solutions used was adjusted by the addition of either dilute

HClO₄ or NaOH solution. The ionic strength of solutions was maintained at a constant value of $I=0.1 M$ (NaClO₄).

The absorption spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer (Lambda 3B) spectrophotometer. The pH measurements were made with a Radiometer M 63 pH-meter with a combined glass electrode of the type Radiometer GK 2301C.

All measurements were carried out in 50% (v/v) ethanol-water medium at 25°. Correction of pH readings in partially aqueous solution was made as described by Douheret²⁸.

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